

UNIVERSITY-INDUSTRY PARTNERING FOR E-RESOURCES DEVELOPMENT

– AN APPROACH

Ananda Ramesh

Assistant Librarian,

Rajiv Gandhi Arts & Science College,

Puducherry – 605 007,

Abstract

In the information era, creation and management of resources which ignites knowledge domain in the process of education and research at higher level gains prominence. Higher education today is changing from a conventional way of campus based university into an internet based virtual university (Walmiki and Ramakrishnegowda, 2009). Internet has altered the ways in which the higher education and research activities are carried out. Today, e-resources development is an area required to be explored through intensive research. The process of building strategies to create e-resources requires collaborative efforts from beneficiaries for knowledge creation. Universities and research institutes are highly involved in partnering to develop e-resources through collaborative online libraries. In India, Association of Indian Universities created INFLIBNET to cater the needs of the users through e-resources to promote academic research which facilitates the industries in particular and society in general. Universities are facilitating industries by providing efficient human resources to achieve their goals with available resources. It is also the responsibility of the industries in turn to facilitate the Universities by creating adequate and contemporary resources which may be in the form of e-resources to reach the users at macro level. This paper is administered to study the present status of e-resources to promote higher education and to study the collaborative initiatives of industries with universities to create e-resources for enhanced knowledge dissemination in higher education.

Key Words: *E- Resources, University-Industry Partnering, Higher Education*

Rationale of the study:

To create the business leaders of the future, schools need access to significant resources that enable them to impart a quality education. These resources include personnel (faculty and support); infrastructure and equipment; training and professional development; industry advisors and other technology based needs like e - resources that are expensive to acquire. Universities are increasingly faced with budget constraints that limit their abilities to acquire these resources (Anil Kumar, et.al, 2002). Thus, Industries may come forward with the universities on collaborative basis to facilitate in creation of e-resources.

Discussion on the Analysis of the Study:

Universities are facilitating industries by providing efficient human resources to achieve their goals with available resources. It is also the responsibility of the industries in turn to facilitate the Universities by creating adequate and contemporary resources which may be in the form of e-resources to reach the users at macro level. This paper is administered to study the present status of e-resources promoting higher education and to study the collaborative initiatives of industries with universities to create e-resources for enhanced knowledge dissemination in higher education.

II. Collaborative Initiatives of Industries with Universities to Create E-Resources:

Commercial partnerships are becoming more prevalent in e-resource management for both libraries and publishers. Recently, several technologies/services, including Aqua Browser, Endeca, eRights, Grokker and Scholarly Stats, have gained attention. For these five products, company representatives and customers were invited to provide a profile containing a brief general description of the technology/service, its purpose, the targeted customer base, the relationship or advantages of the product to libraries and resources needed for implementation (Maria Collins, 2006). The advance in networking and communication technology has made the information services available to the users on their desktop. The feature inbuilt in the search and

retrieval of these resources has made the usage to the maximum. Library subscribes to various Bibliographic and full text databases which are of interest to the users.

Table 1.1 – E - Resource Facilities in Central Universities in India

Sl. No.	Central Universities	e-Data base	e-Books	e-journals	Web Based Resources	Industry Collaboration for e-resources
1.	Aligarh Muslim University	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
2.	Assam University	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
3.	Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
4.	Banaras Hindu University	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
5.	Central Agricultural University	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
6.	Indira Gandhi National Open University	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
7.	Jamia Millia Islamia University	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
8.	Jawaharlal Nehru University	Y	Y	Y	Y	N

solely funded by the universities and the study brings to the notice that industrial collaboration in funding and providing e-resource facility is not yet initiated. Thus, this study suggests the universities and industries need to come forward in a collaborative way to facilitate e-resource creation and management to provide quality higher education and research.

Implications and recommendations:

The world intellectual property organization in 2003, with funding from the Japanese funds-in-trust, commissioned a series of national studies in seven Asian countries (namely, China, India, Japan, Philippines, the republic of Korea, Singapore and Thailand) on the “development of university-industry partnerships for the promotion of innovation and transfer of technology”. The objective was to understand current developments in this field in each country, by presenting quantitative and qualitative data on university-industry partnerships in the field of innovation and technology transfer, describing the legal framework and main policies adopted to promote university-industry partnerships and analyzing factors. As far as collaboration for e-resources it is the need of the hour and has to be initiated in the countries especially in India to facilitate higher education as in the case of technological innovation in other area of collaborative efforts of university and industries.

As a first step, UGC has initiated the UGC-Infonet Digital Library Consortium which was formally launched in December 2003 has proven to be a boon to higher education system in the country and provided current as well as archival access to more than 8000 core and peer-reviewed journals and bibliographic databases in different disciplines. But, the project was closed on 30th March 2012. To satisfy the needs of e-resources of colleges in india N-LIST programme was initiated by Ministry of Human Resource Development under National Mission on Education through ICT. The National Library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Content (N-LIST), being jointly executed by the UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortium, INFLIBNET Centre and the INDEST-AICTE Consortium, IIT Delhi provides access to e-resources to students, researchers and faculty from colleges and other beneficiary institutions through servers installed at the INFLIBNET Centre. As on June 2013, a total number of 3351 colleges have registered themselves with the N-LIST programme. According to Williams (2006), academic libraries spend millions of dollars a year on e-resources, yet many of

them are underutilized and unknown to users. It is very legitimate on the part of the librarians to know whether the academic community is using these e-resources optimally. Consortium has revolutionized the access of scholarly information in form of e-resources to all without any discrimination. Availability of e-resources have played major role in increase in research output globally. According to Web of Science, research output has almost doubled in India since the e-resources are easily accessible. This is more so, after the consortium has brought about access to latest research published in peer reviewed journals within easy reach of researchers.

The effort of the UGC in creating the consortia for facilitating e-resources to improve the standard of higher education to provide quality human resources to the industries is laudable. As per the finding of the study the participation of the industries in funding for e-resources is not initiated till now. Thus, the industries may come forward to facilitate the universities to create quality human resources through facilitating e-resources for promoting higher education and research in innovation in all arenas.

Conclusion:

In the digital era, creation of resources which ignites knowledge domain in the process of education and research at higher level gains prominence. Today, e-resources development is an area required to be explored through intensive research. In the process of building strategies to create e-resources requires collaborative efforts from beneficiaries for knowledge creation. Universities and research institutes are highly involved in partnering to develop e-resources through collaborative online libraries. In India, Association of Indian Universities created INFLIBNET to cater the needs of the users through e-resources to support teaching and to promote academic research which facilitates the industries in particular and society in general. Universities are facilitating industries by providing efficient human resources to achieve their goals with available resources. It is also the responsibility of the industries in turn to facilitate the Universities by creating adequate and contemporary resources in a collaborative way as in the case of industries funding through MOUs in private professional institutes, Industries may also collaborate with universities to facilitate with e-resources to reach the users at macro level to enhance the stratum of higher education.

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